

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND NEW PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES USED IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559874>

Abstract. *The article analyzes the reforms in the education system of the country and their importance, issues of raising inclusive education, the pedagogical significance of the concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2025*

Keywords: *education, forms of education, inclusive education, UNCPRD, UNICEF, pedagogical analysis, method, social policy.*

ИНКЛЮЗИВНОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НОВЫЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ, ИСПОЛЬЗУЕМЫЕ В СИСТЕМЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. *В статье анализируются реформы в системе образования страны и их значение, вопросы повышения уровня инклюзивного образования, педагогическая значимость концепции развития инклюзивного образования в системе государственного образования на 2020-2025 гг.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, формы образования, инклюзивное образование, UNCPRD, UNICEF, педагогический анализ, методика, социальная политика.*

Introduction. Special education has developed as an educational system for children with disabilities. It is built on the assumption that the needs of children with disabilities cannot be met in general education institutions. Special education operates all over the world in the form of schools or boarding schools, as well as small parts of general education schools. Education of children with special needs in the special education system makes it difficult for them to adapt to society after finishing school. It also forces them to stay away from their families. This category of children gets used to being taken care of, and they have difficulties in self-care. In addition, many children with special needs are excluded from education.

Currently, in our Republic, inclusive education policy is being implemented in order to make children with special needs receive education in special or general education system according to their development level, characteristics of disabilities and abilities. Placing a disabled child in a normal environment is the first step towards integration. Inclusive education is based on the social model, which believes that the problem is not in the child, but in the program and methodology. This requires making some changes to the education system. In this case, educational plans are prepared taking into account the needs of each child, and aspects of the methodology related to psychological problems are put on the right track.

Inclusive education concludes that all children, including disabled children, can study in the school they want. The reason for a child becoming disabled is society, environment, misunderstandings, and mistakes. Therefore, this society must sacrifice itself for his education. In inclusive education, the physical conditions at school also play an important role.

To put it simply, students enter the doors of all schools through the stairs. But disabled children in special wheelchairs cannot climb these stairs, even children walking on crutches

may have difficulty. Therefore, it is necessary to create comfortable conditions for healthy children and disabled children to pass through the stairs and doors.

Main body. Inclusive education allows children with special needs to always be in their family neighborhood and in the circle of relatives. Placement of children in boarding schools far away from their family and home prevents their right to participate in the life of their home, family and community. A child who is far from his home, family, and parental love grows up with a hard time. Because the family is the main center of education.

Inclusive education can serve as a catalyst for improving the quality of education. Admission of children with special needs to general education institutions encourages students to develop new teaching methods that are more child-centered and more inclusive. And the benefit of this affects every child. Inclusive education helps prevent discrimination.

Misconceptions and attitudes towards people with disabilities are very high in society. The reason for this may be the lack of information about them and their closed education in special institutions from a young age. Losing or reducing such an attitude is a very difficult task. But it is known from experience that compared to adults, children understand differences and similarities faster. If children with special needs receive education together with children with normal development, it would ensure that all children with disabilities realize that they are children like themselves and do not discriminate. One of the most urgent problems today is the issue of important tasks and the situation in the system related to children in need of social protection.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, deep reforms and changes are taking place in the system of social protection of children, as in all areas. The interpretation of new ideas on inclusive education requires national, organizational and methodological reforms. Children with special educational needs are children whose needs are not being met by the current school system. For this reason, schools should respond to the diverse and common goals, aspirations, and interests of all children and ensure their education. At the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in September 2017, the draft of the International Convention "On the Rights of Youth" was developed. "The rights of young people are, first and foremost, their right to a peaceful and healthy life and education ensuring that our growing young generation matures and receives high-quality and excellent education is always a priority for us.(2)

"According to the provisions of Article 41 of our General Dictionary and Article 5 of the Newly Revised Law "On Education" (September 23, 2020), everyone has equal rights to education [2]. This law differs from the previous edition by introducing the concept of inclusive (harmonized) education, and according to this law, the Cabinet of Ministers is designated as the competent body in the field of inclusive education. From this point of view, it is important to equally develop the inclusive form of education in our country. The English term "inclusive" means integration, cooperative education, and is recognized by the world community as the most humane and effective education.

Inclusive education is the provision of equal rights to education in educational institutions, taking into account the differences in special educational needs and individual capabilities for all students.

Currently, the recognition of inclusive education in all countries does not depend only on passing laws. Fighting discrimination and social prejudice is the most important thing. In other words, it is the first time to carry out propaganda activities among the population, recognizing inclusive education. Since 1990, a number of declarations and decisions have been adopted at the global level regarding the education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions.

Many countries of the world recognized them. In 2006, the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCPRD) was adopted. This document was ratified by our country on February 27, 2009. Article 24 of this Convention states: "Participating states recognize the right of persons with disabilities to receive education.

Participating countries shall ensure inclusive education at all levels and lifelong learning in order to realize this right without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunities. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the analysis and initial assessment of disabled children began in 1966. In November 1996, based on the initiative of the National Commission of Uzbekistan for UNESCO, a national curriculum on "Inclusive methods in the field of special education" was successfully implemented in Tashkent. In October 1998, a regional conference on this topic was organized in Bukhara. This conference was held in cooperation with UNESCO, UNICEF (UN Children's Fund), World Health Organization and International Labor Organization. As a result of these activities, a resource center on inclusive education was established under the Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan in 2001. Until now, several educational seminars have been held by this center. The project "Inclusive education for children with special needs in Uzbekistan" has been implemented since 2014, and more than 900 boys and girls with special needs were involved in general education in schools and preschools. (7)

Members of medical, psychological and pedagogical commissions and teaching staff were trained on providing inclusive services in the field of education. Five pilot resource centers were established in different regions of our country, where educational-methodical, legal, and advisory support was provided for children with special needs, their parents, and experts. The creation of the educational modules "Fundamentals of inclusive education", "Children with special needs in general education", "Organization of an inclusive school", further improvement of the educational process in this direction, improvement of professional skills of pedagogues allowed. It is the moral duty of the country to its citizens to support children who need inclusive education due to physical disabilities, to develop and put into practice the necessary conditions and mechanisms for their socialization. Based on the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs" PD-4860 2020-2025 Concept of development of inclusive education in public education system was approved in -years. (1)

The following results are expected by performing the tasks defined within the framework of the concept:

-the role of inclusive education as a strategic factor in the development, rehabilitation, and integration of people with special educational needs into society is confirmed;

-the integrity of the educational environment of children with special educational needs is strengthened, the necessary conditions for their integration into society are provided;

-mechanisms for coordinating the interests of the state, society, and individual in the field of inclusive education will be created;

-the general convenience, continuity, quality of education, as well as the level of development, flexibility and variability of the characteristics of the students are achieved;

-cooperation relations will be strengthened within the framework of international relations in the field of inclusive education;

-they are supported by the state in order for students to receive quality education, taking into account the uniqueness of their educational needs;

-through the gradual introduction of inclusive education, specialized educational institutions for children with special educational needs will be optimized, students studying in them will receive education in general educational institutions as equal members of society;

-training of personnel based on inclusive education programs will be launched in pedagogical higher education institutions;

-the material and technical base of inclusive educational institutions will be improved;

-full connection of inclusive educational institutions to the Internet network is ensured;

-a mechanism for the provision of public services will be introduced to accept students in inclusive educational institutions and transfer them to other educational institutions.

Conclusion. In sum up inclusive education ensures that people with disabilities receive education along with their social peers, and (if there are no serious reasons for their development) they are admitted to regular schools. In some cases, children with severe disabilities receive education with the help of correctional programs in special schools and special rehabilitation centers or in special classes at regular schools. In these schools, it is planned to provide education taking into account the needs of the child.

Many reforms are being implemented in our country to eliminate these shortcomings.

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